

Reproducibility Unveiled: A Comprehensive Investigation into 'Reliability Prediction for Health-related Content'—A Study Replication and Findings Validation

MIHNEA ALEMAN, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

IVAN BABIY, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

YAT HIN CHAN, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

AHMED ŠABANOVIĆ, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

Addressing the challenge of ascertaining the reliability of online data has gathered recent attention, particularly heightened by the surge in unreliable health-related content post-COVID-19. Previous research [1] tackled this issue through the application of linguistic-based features. In our study, our aim is to replicate the code employed by the original authors. Our study demonstrates a strong alignment of performance with the results reported by the original authors. Additionally, our replication study validates the credibility of their conclusions. We provide a detailed account of encountered challenges during replication, highlighting instances of outdated libraries and faulty code. Lastly, our work contributes insights by incorporating significance tests to assess differences between specific features.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing prevalence of online health-related content, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, has underscored the critical need to determine the reliability of such information. In response to this challenge, the paper [1] delves into the realm of reliability prediction using standard classification technology. This study builds upon prior research, including the work conducted by Sondhi et al. [5], and aims to contribute to the research community by replicating the experiment.

Our group undertook the challenge to replicate the predictive technology developed by Fernández-Pichel and his colleagues utilizing Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning techniques. They also provided three test datasets and a set of features that served as the foundation for our replication.

The successful recreation of results from the original study would not only validate but also strengthen the conclusions drawn in their research. This replication initiative is crucial for establishing the relevance of contemporary technology and its potential application in filtering non-reliable content.

To achieve this, we thoroughly examined and re-implemented the code proposed by the original authors. Maintaining consistency, we applied the same experimental methodology and performance metrics as outlined in the original paper. Additionally, a final section is dedicated to conducting significance tests to assess whether the paper's proposed improvements are statistically significant, meaning they are unlikely to have occurred by chance.

Table 1. Class distribution across different datasets

Class	Sondhi et al.	Schwarz et al.	CLEF eHEALTH
Reliable	180	75	9879
Unreliable	180	5	3607

As we delve into the report, we will outline the experimental setup, features considered, challenges faced during replication, and the results obtained. Our analysis goes beyond simple reproduction, aiming to contribute valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on the reliability of health-related content prediction.

The code of our reproducibility experiment is available on Github¹.

2 DATASETS

The authors in the original paper manually generated a well-balanced dataset comprising both reliable and unreliable webpages. They randomly chose positive pages from HON2-accredited websites and actively searched for low-quality pages using specific queries like disease name + "miracle cure." To prevent topic bias, they conducted a topic analysis on reliable pages, extracting disease-related keywords. Using these keywords, they manually generated queries to identify unreliable pages, ultimately selecting 180 such pages from the search results.

Fernández-Pichel and his colleagues used two other dataset to test the robustness of their model. Schwarz et al.'s Web Search dataset [4] and the CLEF eHealth consumer health search task 2018 [2] were employed to assess this classification technology further. While both datasets include health-related content, the former also encompasses topics like finance, politics, environment, and news about famous people.

Schwarz et al. focused on credibility assessment for online information seekers, while CLEF eHealth addressed a similar issue, specifically for health-related data. Despite lacking reliability labels, credibility and trustworthiness were used as proxies. The authors assessed the generalizability of prior findings across datasets.

Schwarz et al. labeled 1000 webpages using a five-point Likert scale. For CLEF eHealth, the dataset was derived from CommonCrawl and organized by domain. The RBP-based method by Moffat et al. [3] formed the assessment pool, assessed by Amazon Mechanical Turk workers using an eleven-point scale. To fit our binary-class technology, both datasets were relabeled into a binary scale.

Table 1 shows the class distribution across all datasets used. to address imbalanced learning, the authors compared two approaches: introducing a cost-factor with a higher penalty for minority class errors and resampling techniques. Our findings, based on superior performance in preliminary experiments, focus on cost-factor methods over resampling. For metric evaluation, they considered micro-averaged F_1 , class-specific F_1 values, prioritizing the minority class or less reliable F_1 metrics during feature combination selection.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We meticulously designed and implemented our reproduction process to closely align with the original experimental setup, outlined in the GitHub repository at <https://github.com/MarcosFP97/Health-Rel>. This section provides a detailed account of our setup, encompassing the hardware and software configurations, data acquisition, and the specific steps undertaken to reproduce the experiments.

¹<https://github.com/leoyhchan/Health-Rel>

105 Despite our efforts to closely align our setup with the authors' original configuration, some differences arose due to
106 practical considerations, but they did not significantly impact the experimental outcomes. While the original study
107 conducted experiments on an Ubuntu 19.04 machine, we utilized a Windows environment. It's important to note that
108 this alteration did not introduce any discernible discrepancies in the experimental results.
109

110 The choice of Windows as the operating system did not compromise the fundamental aspects of the study, such as
111 the implementation of the SVM classifier, feature extraction techniques, and cross-validation procedures. We ensured
112 that the key components, including Python version, libraries, and overall workflow, were consistent with the original
113 setup, thereby minimizing the likelihood of divergent results.
114

115 A pivotal aspect contributing to the success of our reproduction effort was the comprehensive availability of all
116 necessary data in the GitHub repository provided by the authors. The complete accessibility of data in GitHub not
117 only streamlined the reproduction process but also exemplifies good research practices, fostering transparency and
118 facilitating collaborative efforts within the scientific community.
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120 In the course of our reproduction process, we encountered several challenges, as outlined below. These issues required
121 careful consideration and resolution to ensure the successful replication of the experiments conducted in the original
122 study.
123

124 Due to the considerable size of the CLEF eHealth dataset, which surpassed the capacities of our local computing
125 resources, we encountered practical constraints that prevented us from conducting a direct reproduction of the
126 experiments.
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128 The original paper's experimental setup involved a server configuration boasting substantial resources, including
129 377 GB of RAM and 15 terabytes of storage. Unfortunately, our local infrastructure did not match these specifications,
130 necessitating access to comparable server resources for an accurate replication. Given these limitations, we decided to
131 forego replicating the experiments on the CLEF eHealth dataset.
132

133 Compatibility challenges arose from the original `build.sh` script, which was designed for Bash and posed difficulties
134 on our Windows-based operating systems. To address this, we opted to execute the code directly from the command
135 prompt.
136

137 The omission of the `chmod` command in our execution process prompted a necessary adjustment to ensure proper
138 permissions.
139

140 Given the variation in file path conventions between operating systems, we modified the file paths containing `/s` to
141 use `\\s` on Windows.
142

143 Building the SVMlight dependency necessitated the presence of a C++ compiler. We acquired the appropriate compiler
144 for Windows from Microsoft² to fulfill this prerequisite.
145

146 A discrepancy arose in the implementation of a wrapper for the `isnan()` function in C by the original authors.
147 Since `isnan()` is already a macro in C, this led to compilation failures. To resolve this, we commented out the wrapper,
148 allowing for successful code compilation.
149

150 A notable departure in our reproduction process was the introduction of variability through the utilization of
151 multiple random seeds during the experiments, a practice not explicitly employed by the authors in the original study.
152 Recognizing the potential impact of randomization on the experimental outcomes, we adopted a strategy to enhance the
153 robustness of our results. In contrast to the single-run experiments conducted in the original paper, we employed five
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155 ²<https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/cpp/build/building-on-the-command-line?view=msvc-170>
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Table 2. Appendix

A. Code/Setup Difficulties	B. Data	C. Process
Code not provided	Data not provided	Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed
Code partially not provided	Data partially not provided ✓	Experimental setup not described
Faulty code provided	Metadata not provided ✓	Experiment workflow incomplete
Information about software versions missing		Inconsistencies in paper, code, and data
Specific hardware and software setup necessary ✓		Results differ significantly

different seeds for each experiment setup. By systematically incorporating diverse seeds, we aimed to unveil potential fluctuations in the results that could arise from different initializations.

In addition to the congruence in our experiment setup with that outlined by the authors, it is noteworthy that the code provided by the authors ran seamlessly without encountering any issues. The absence of complications in running the provided code contributes to the robustness of our reproduction, as it ensures that the implementation closely adheres to the authors’ methodology.

4 RESULTS

Our focus is on uncovering any divergences from the original findings, offering insights derived from extended evaluations. This section provides a succinct overview of the reproducibility and performance of the predictive models, shedding light on their robustness and generalizability.

Our reproduction of the paper’s experiments proved successful, faithfully adhering to the outlined methodologies and adapting where necessary to accommodate variations in computing environments. Our results align closely with those reported in the original paper.

The consistent findings reaffirm the robustness and reproducibility of the predictive models, validating the accuracy of our implementation and emphasizing the reliability of the experiment under scrutiny. This successful replication serves as a crucial step in confirming the soundness of the original study’s experimental design and reinforces the credibility of the reported outcomes.

A noteworthy distinction in our reproduction process lies in our deliberate choice to run the experiments multiple times, a departure from the original paper’s approach where experiments were conducted as single runs. This departure allowed us to systematically explore the robustness and stability of the predictive models under diverse conditions.

The decision to run experiments multiple times offers a more comprehensive perspective, capturing potential fluctuations in results due to different initializations. While the authors of the original paper did not adopt this practice, our methodological enhancement contributes to a nuanced understanding of the reliability prediction technology’s performance and its sensitivity to variations in experimental runs.

It is also worth noticing that the authors of the original paper did not explicitly provide information regarding the variance in their results.

Despite introducing variability through multiple seed runs in our experiments, it is noteworthy that all the key conclusions drawn from the original paper persist. The consistency of findings across diverse seeds reaffirms the robustness and reliability of the predictions. Our meticulous approach to exploration ensures that the models' effectiveness and the implications of its application remain steadfast, validating the initial conclusions made by the authors.

4.1 Significance test

In addition to reproducing previous work to assess generalisability, Fernández-Pichel et al. also suggested that keeping stop words and applying standardisation as a pre-processing step would yield better prediction outcome in the case of predicting reliability of health-related content. However, the aforementioned claims were made based on having only run cross-validation on one seed, and averaging the scores. Therefore, we repeated the experiments under multiple seeds to produce more cross-validation scores, and tested whether the improvements are statistically significance.

To test these 2 claims, we ran additional experiments on the Sondhi dataset under different settings under 2 random seeds, and 3 cost factors, under each seed wit the same cross-validation folds. We then extracted the cross-validation scores of each fold and ran **one-sided paired sample t-tests** to test for statistical significance in improvement.

4.2 The effect of standardisation

We ran cross-validation on with the following variables held constant:

- Dataset: Sondhi
- Feature set: All features
- Pre-processing: Keep stop words

And compared resulting metrics with and without standardisation. We set the significance level of our null hypothesis significance test at $\alpha = 0.05$, with below hypotheses.

H_0 : Metrics with standardisation = Metrics without standardisation

H_A : Metrics with standardisation > Metrics without standardisation

Metric	Accuracy	F_1 (Micro-averaged)	F_1 (Reliable class)	F_1 (Unreliable class)
p -value	4.897×10^{-7}	3.776×10^{-10}	8.352×10^{-10}	1.379×10^{-9}

Table 3. p -values for significance test of improvement over standardisation

At $\alpha = 0.05$, we reject H_0 that prediction performance with and without standardisation are the same based on all metrics.

4.3 The effect of stop word removal

We ran cross-validation on with the following variables held constant:

- Dataset: Sondhi
- Feature set: All features
- Pre-processing: Standaridsation

And compared resulting metrics when keeping and removing stop words. We set the significance level of our null hypothesis significance test at $\alpha = 0.05$, with below hypotheses.

H_0 : Metrics when keeping stop words = Metrics when keeping stop words

261 H_A : Metrics when keeping stop words > Metrics when keeping stop words

262

Metric	Accuracy	F_1 (Micro-averaged)	F_1 (Reliable class)	F_1 (Unreliable class)
p -value	0.0101	0.2068	0.7366	0.0211

263
264
265 Table 4. p -values for significance test of improvement when keeping over removing stop words

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267

268 At $\alpha = 0.05$, we cannot reject H_0 that prediction performance when keeping and removing stop words are the same
269 for all metrics. However, it is worth noting that the improvement of F_1 score of the unreliable class, the class of interest,
270 is statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

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5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we partially reproduced a study that attempted to test the generalisability of predicting the reliability of online health-related information. The reproduction was successful. However, since we did not cover one of the datasets used by Fernández-Piche et al., this reproduction does not fully confirm that the prediction technique can be generalised to data sets other than the one used by Sondhi. Moreover, further testing suggests that while the proposed standardisation technique indeed improves prediction performance, it is less clear whether keeping stop words is generally beneficial.

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